

INTEGRATION OF FUZZY CARBON OVERBRAIDS INTO STRUCTURAL MEMBERS FOR IMPROVED COMPRESSIVE PERFORMANCE

Iheoma Chigoziri Nwuzor, Laura Rhian Pickard,
Bohao Zhang, Xiaodong Xu, Nicolas Darras, Ian Lee,
Kawthar Alkateb, Curtis Wong, Darren Lo,
Giuliano Allegri, Michael R Wisnom, & Richard S Trask

Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol

Laura.Pickard@Bristol.ac.uk

IMPERIAL

The Composites Centre

for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

Bristol Composites Institute

UK Research
and Innovation

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

NEXT GENERATION FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

A full scale redesign for compression

NextCOMP takes inspiration from the hierarchical structure of natural materials

Illustration of the structure of human compact bone, a biological, hierarchical composite. Adapted from R. Lakes, "Materials with structural hierarchy," *Nature*, vol. 361, no. 6412, pp. 511–515, Feb. 1993, doi: 10.1038/361511a0.

HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES

Mechanistic modelling

Resin systems

Ply level systems

In-Situ mechanistic studies

Fibre platforms

Bundle systems

HIERARCHICAL APPROACH: BUNDLE SYSTEMS

Top left: pultruded carbon fibre-epoxy rods. Bottom left: Microscope image of rod cross sections. Top right: Strut. Bottom right: X-ray CT slice showing cross section of strut.

CYLINDRICAL STRUCT MANUFACTURE

Church lane bridge over A4174, Google maps

- Initial trial used flexible mould with outer constraint
- Moved to fixed multi-part mould for geometrical regularity
- Resin heated and injected at $5 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$
- Porosity below limit of detection in Nikon XTH-320 X-ray CT scanner
- Optimisation of packing
- Material hybridisation
- Tested in buckling

Manufacturing approach with flexible mould

Fixed geometry multi part mould

OVERWINDING AND OVERBRAIDING

Samples from Potter et al 2000, CT scans L R Pickard. Following compression after impact tests. Overwound strut (left) exhibited greater compressive strength than without overwind (centre, right)

- Can we apply this in a hierarchical manner?
 - Overbraid individual rods
 - Constrain kink band formation at rod level

Herzog microbraider with 8 tows PBO 273dtex overbraiding pultruded rod.

EXPECTED EFFECT OF OVERBRAIDING RODS

- Model 'halo' of shear support around rod based on fit to data

$$\sigma_{shear} = G_1(1 - e^{-G_2 \varepsilon})$$

- G1 increase in Halo
- G2 increase in Halo
- G1 increase in matrix too
- G2 increase in matrix too

- How can we create this extended zone of shear support?

FUZZY CARBON OVERBRAIDS

Left: diagram illustrating lay length.

Right: X-ray CT scan of Strut consisting of pultruded rods with fuzzy carbon overbraids, image I. Nwuzor

- Short lay length with brittle fibres-> fuzzy effect
- Fuzzy carbon-> shear support in wide region around rod
 - Plain vs overbraided rods
 - Different lay lengths

Rods overbraided with Zylon (left) and fuzzy Carbon

L. R. Pickard, G. Allegri, and M. R. Wisnom, ECCM20., 2022
DOI: 10.5075/epfl-298799_978-2-9701614-0-0

TESTING AND ANALYSIS

- Strut trimmed to 300mm
- 3 strain gauges around centre at 120 degree spacing
- X-ray CT imaging
- Strut tested in eccentric buckling at 3mm/min

X-ray CT cross section of strut showing strain gauges

TESTING AND ANALYSIS

- Strut trimmed to 300mm
- 3 strain gauges around centre at 120 degree spacing
- X-ray CT imaging
- Strut tested in eccentric buckling at 3mm/min

X-ray CT cross section of strut showing strain gauges

TESTING AND ANALYSIS

- Strut trimmed to 300mm
- 3 strain gauges around centre at 120 degree spacing
- X-ray CT imaging
- Strut tested in eccentric buckling at 3mm/min

X-ray CT cross section of strut showing strain gauges

FRACTOGRAPHY EXAMPLES

Cr_Z 2024-03-11 mMU x30 2 mm

Failure surface of strut with
plain rods, no overbraids

FRACTOGRAPHY EXAMPLES

Cr_Z 2024-03-11 mMU x30 2 mm

Cr_Z mMU x25 4 mm

Failure surface of strut with plain rods, no overbraids

Failure surface of strut with 6mm lay length overbraids

FRACTOGRAPHY EXAMPLES

Cr_Z 2024-03-11 mMU x30 2 mm

Cr_Z mMU x25 4 mm

Cr_Z mMU x30 2 mm

Failure surface of strut with plain rods, no overbraids

Failure surface of strut with 6mm lay length overbraids

Failure surface of strut with 2.5mm lay length overbraids (fuzzy)

FRACTOGRAPHY EXAMPLES

Failure surface of strut with plain rods, no overbraids

Failure surface of strut with 6mm lay length overbraids

Failure surface of strut with 2.5mm lay length overbraids (fuzzy)

KEY RESULTS

- Struts with 0.8mm diameter rods manufactured and tested in buckling:
 - Plain rods, no overbraids
 - 8 x 1k T300 carbon fibre overbraids of lay length:
 - 2.5mm, fuzzy carbon
 - 4mm
 - 6mm
- Struts with 2.5mm lay length overbraids failed in **tension**, all others in **compression**
 - Indicates improved performance in compression with fuzzy carbon overbraid
- Hybridised carbon/aramid overbraids can improve packing while keeping 'fuzzy carbon' aspect
- 4x 1 T300 carbon fibre and 4x aramid initial trials carried out
 - Both tensile and compressive failure seen

SUMMARY

- Hierarchical, biomimetic composite structures offer a new design space
- Struts made with pultruded rod elements are suitable for use in a variety of applications
- Overbraiding rods with carbon creates a 'fuzzy' effect at low lay length due to partial breakage
 - Increase fibre-resin contact region
 - Shear support of fibre
 - Initial results indicate change in failure mode under buckling
 - Increased performance under compression

Next
COMP

Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

I would like to acknowledge funding which supported this work from the UK Research and Innovation - EPSRC Programme Grant; Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites: A Full Scale Redesign for Compression (EP/T011653/1)

A collaboration between Imperial College London and University of Bristol

IMPERIAL

University of
BRISTOL

Bristol Composites Institute

